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**Usability and communication values of mobile applications in AR and
VR technology in the assessment of consumers from Generation Z**

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Introduction	3
1. Generation Z as a Subject of Communication in Virtual Environments	5
1.1 The Concept of Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) and Features of Communication in Virtual Environments.....	5
1.2 Characteristics of Generation Z Compared with Other Consumer Types	10
2. Characteristics of mobile applications as a communication tool	18
2.1 Technologies used in mobile communication	18
2.2 Features, scope of use, and design principles of mobile applications	21
2.3 Characteristics of Selected Mobile Applications in VR and AR Technology	28
3. Evaluation of Mobile Applications as a Communication Tool in the Light of a Usability Test 37	
3.1 Research Methodology	37
3.2 Evaluation of AR Technology Applications	39
3.3 Evaluation of VR Technology Applications	41
Conclusion.....	43
Bibliography	45
List of Figures	49
List of Tables	49
Appendix	50

Introduction

Mobile applications are among the most modern and innovative communication tools—especially those based on AR (Augmented Reality) and VR (Virtual Reality) technologies. Ongoing social changes—most notably the gradual entry of consumers born after 1995, i.e., Generation Z—are reshaping the marketing-communication and image-building methods used by companies. Generation Z is the first cohort raised with unrestricted access to the Internet. Reaching this market segment effectively is therefore a considerable challenge for contemporary business. Monitoring technological trends and the new solutions that attract young people is essential, because failing to adapt products and services to them can diminish a brand's attractiveness.

The primary objective of this thesis is to identify the possibilities of using AR- and VR-enabled mobile applications as a communication channel between companies and young consumers. A secondary objective is to determine the characteristic features of Generation Z, the main target of these new technological communication solutions.

The study evaluates selected AR and VR mobile applications in terms of innovation, user-experience design, user interface, attention absorption and educational value. The research sample comprised young people aged 15–21—representatives of Generation Z. The analysis covers the period 2003–2018.

The thesis posits that although VR technology exerts a stronger experiential impact, its communication potential is lower than that of AR.

Research Hypotheses:

- Among Generation Z users, gaze-targeting control enjoys the greatest interest.
- General UX design principles applied to conventional mobile apps work equally well when designing AR applications.
- For users, the visual aesthetics of an AR/VR mobile app are as important as intuitive navigation.
- VR applications negatively affect the user's visual system.

The theoretical section draws on a critical analysis of the literature and logical reasoning. Both primary and secondary sources are used.

Market-research reports from the past three years—mainly English-language—help profile Generation Z relative to other cohorts and gauge the market potential for AR and VR mobile apps. The empirical section rests on usability-testing results obtained through the author’s own research. Thinking-aloud protocols were incorporated to gather precise, aggregable data. The purposive sample consisted of Generation Z individuals born between 1996 and 2000; usability tests were conducted in May 2018.

Chapter 1 characterises the features of virtual communication and their influence on modern buyers, detailing how these traits vary among generations, with particular attention to Generation Z. Chapter 2 describes smartphone-based VR and AR technologies, the tools used to create them, and key design principles, illustrated by six example apps: Anatomy 4D (AR), Google Translate (AR), Pokémon Go (AR), Titans of Space (VR), Lost in the Kismet (VR) and Public Speaking (VR). Chapter 3 presents usability-test findings for these applications, analysing user opinions and preferences regarding UX and UI. The chapter verifies the research hypotheses; results and broader conclusions appear in the final section.

1 . Generation Z as a Subject of Communication in Virtual Environments

1.1 The Concept of Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR) and Features of Communication in Virtual Environments

Virtual Reality (VR) is based on a computer-generated three-dimensional environment that allows the user to move within it and interact (Guttentag 2010). R. Kayne (2014) defines Augmented Reality (AR) as an interactive, computer-generated virtual world that may be static or dynamic.

Augmented Reality primarily overlays the real world with computer-generated elements that take a graphic form (Hyun, Lee & Hu 2009). E. Azuma (1993) describes AR as a system that merges the real and virtual worlds, operates interactively in real time and allows freedom of movement in three dimensions. It does not create a new virtual environment; rather, it supplements the real one. A. McNamara (2016) sees AR as a technology that enriches the real world with virtual information, helping consumers understand it better and increasing satisfaction and usability of their immediate surroundings.

Alongside the concepts of virtual and augmented reality, it is also necessary to define the notion of the consumer, because the term new consumer frequently appears in this context. In marketing literature a consumer is an economic entity that consumes purchased products—goods or services. The term is often used interchangeably with buyer, user, or client, yet these categories are not identical. A buyer is an entity that purchases goods on the market in order to satisfy needs—its own or those of other individuals. Thus a buyer may sometimes act merely as the representative of the final consumer without actually being that consumer. A client, by contrast, can be any economic entity—such as a business, private person, or institution—interested in acquiring a given good or service (Kiezel [ed.] 2010, p. 29).

The differences between the consumer and the buyer are highlighted by M. Solomon (2006, p. 25). According to the author, the consumer is the 'protagonist' of the three stages of consumption (Figure 1): first identifying a desire or need, then purchasing, and finally consuming the acquired product (Berbeka 2016).

Figure 1. Consumer behavior

Source: Kieźel (ed.), 2010, p. 45

This study examines consumer behavior toward products delivered through VR and AR technologies. “New consumers” — members of Generation Z — tend to distrust products and struggle with a lack of free time for pursuing interests, entertainment, and hobbies. They orient their actions and purchase decisions toward saving time, place less trust in their surroundings, and, when searching for products, focus on the highest quality while relying less and less on information from traditional forms of advertising (Kos-Łabędowicz, 2015, p. 10).

Table 1. Key differences between the traditional consumer and the new-era consumer

Traditional consumer	New-era consumer
Seeks convenience	Seeks authenticity
Adapts to the market	Emphasises individuality
Less engaged	Engaged
Conformist	Independent
Less informed	Well-informed

Source: Małysa-Kaleta, 2003, p. 78.

Consumers are attracted to virtual- and augmented-reality technologies chiefly because they seek new sensations and experiences. The product itself is no longer the key “commodity”; what counts are the benefits it brings—namely the customer’s emotions, impressions, and lived experiences. This trend spans several spheres and industries, notably entertainment and education. VR and AR fit perfectly, supplying sensations and experiences that were previously unknown. Because these technologies stimulate the senses—above all sight, and most consumers are famously “visual learners”—they enhance the effectiveness of communication (Berbeka 2016, p. 87).

Internet communication differs greatly from everyday face-to-face interaction: online we do not see our interlocutor's facial expressions, gestures, or hear the full color and tone of the voice. Over time, online exchange has developed its own rules, embodied in netiquette—guidelines for proper behavior on the Internet (Wikipedia, n.d.). Breaking netiquette can bring consequences such as abuse reports or an administrator cutting the offender off from the service.

Despite their differences, traditional and online communication share the same aims: conveying a message, sparking discussion, or providing information. Online interaction has its own limits, strengths, and specific traits, yet the two modes overlap in several ways (heuristic, n.d.):

- Mutual influence between sender and receiver;
- Dynamic back-and-forth of conversation;
- Use of symbols intelligible to both sides, plus signs tied to context or culture;
- A fundamentally social process, involving at least two people rather than occurring in isolation.

In everyday life we convey emotions through laughter, shouting, gestures, or by stating them outright. Tone of voice and the words we choose also reveal how we feel. Online, in turn, emotions are described or expressed with *emoticons*—typographic ideograms for showing mood (many apps render them as graphic *emoji*) (Wikipedia, n.d.)—that visualise feelings. Yet the most common medium remains the written word, which, unfortunately, does not present the interlocutor directly; one can only infer their attitude, social status, appearance, and emotions. For companies whose activity relies on the specifics of the internet, the recipient's first impression is crucial. Online communication faces risks such as impersonation or anonymous insults, which often go unpunished.

Key characteristics of online communication include (heuristic, n.d.):

- **No territorial limits** – Private, entertainment, and business exchanges can occur from anywhere in the world, provided there is internet access. A user can now be “virtually” in several places at once: for example, attending an online training session while at work. Contact is instantaneous via e-mail and a range of messaging apps. Importantly, communication is not restricted to text; applications also let us hear and see the other

party. Figure 2 lists the world’s most popular messengers: WhatsApp ranks first, followed by Facebook Messenger—both owned by Meta (formerly Facebook Inc.). These apps erase territorial barriers, enabling firms to expand and distribute their products or services beyond their home country.

- **Social diversity** – The web is widely accessible and easy to use, opening the door to interactions with people from many social strata. In offline life we exist within fairly defined groups and recognize our membership in them, whereas online those boundaries blur. One can meet individuals otherwise impossible to encounter, creating unprecedented opportunities for transactions and business partnerships. Cyberspace also links disparate groups, fostering communication, exchange of views, and discussion. Notably, online interlocutors move rapidly to an informal tone, addressing each other by first name; in casual internet conversations, polite forms such as “Mr/Ms” appear rarely, regardless of age differences.

Figure 2. Monthly active users (in millions) of the most popular mobile communication apps

Source: Statista, 2018

- **Anonymity** – Online, it is easy to remain anonymous, although this is not always possible if one neglects personal-data security. Every company authorised to process personal information is obliged to protect it, and whenever you reveal your data you should first read the organization’s privacy policy. Anonymity also carries the risk of encountering people who impersonate others. This danger is serious not only for children, who may meet criminals while surfing the web, but also for anyone using online services or shopping. The law seeks to protect consumers, yet vigilance and common sense are crucial; references, comments, and reviews become invaluable safeguards. Reputable e-businesses welcome dialogue and cooperation, demonstrating that they have nothing to hide from customers.
- **No time constraints** – Another advantage of online communication is that it can take place virtually 24 / 7, the only requirement being an internet connection. It is extremely cheap, fast, and accessible. Never before in human history have people been able to converse on such a scale or access such vast amounts of knowledge. Today’s society is an information society, which fuels the growth of e-business and broad interest in it. A company operating online is effectively “open” all the time, so customers are no longer tied to fixed opening hours as they are with brick-and-mortar shops.
- **Limited sensory perception** – The internet also reduces our ability to read an interlocutor’s emotional stance: without tone of voice or facial expressions, it is hard to judge whether the person is positive or hostile. Because online exchanges usually rely on text and lack visual contact, intentions can be misread and the same message interpreted in multiple ways. Emoticons were introduced to mitigate this problem. While perfectly normal in private chats, they can appear unprofessional in a purely business setting; partners who maintain strictly formal relations may view them as over-familiar. Official e-mails, letters, and messages should therefore observe professional standards. Without observing the recipient’s reactions, misunderstandings arise easily. Once mutual understanding has been established through good, collegial relations, visual aids and other embellishments can help deepen healthy ties, revealing the “human face” behind the screen.

- **Archiving conversations** – Most internet tools allow previous messages to be stored in a searchable archive, accessible at any time. This is immensely valuable for any online business, as it lets staff review past exchanges and craft more precise responses.

In the 21st century, the ease and accessibility of communication via the Internet are unlimited. However, for it to have a positive impact on people's lives, it is important to use it with respect for others and in accordance with ethical principles. Online communication differs from traditional communication, but it still always relates to another person and a specific social process.

1.2 Characteristics of Generation Z Compared with Other Consumer Types

Shifting market conditions—greater access to information, rapid technological advances, expanding product supply, and the sheer volume of stimuli aimed at buyers—along with changes in the consumers themselves (generational turnover and the arrival of new cohorts) make it possible to distinguish several broad consumer types (businessinsider, n.d.).

Social scientists note that to speak of a generation, its members must be linked by a distinctive bond: shared beliefs and values. Often that internal glue is a collective generational experience (for example, the imposition of martial law in Poland or the 9/11 attacks). A further marker of a generational boundary is the emergence of conflict between the “young” and the “old.”

Although birth year is the primary criterion—essentially dividing the younger from the older—other factors also matter: worldview, attitude toward life, and personal convictions. Even within a single generation, people can differ markedly not only in age but also in the values they hold, their outlook on the future, and their range of experiences. Consequently, firms operating in a given market must tailor their offerings to the evolving expectations and preferences of each consumer generation.

Table 2. Differences Between Consumer Generations

Generation (birth years)	Maturists (born before 1945)	Baby Boomers (1945 – 1960)	Generation X (1961 – 1980)	Generation Y / Millennials (1981 – 1995)	Generation Z (born after 1995)
Defining events & culture	World War II, fixed gender roles (especially for women), rationing, rock-and-roll, nuclear families	Cold War, "Swinging Sixties," post-war boom, youth culture, moon landing, family orientation, Woodstock, rise of teenagers' influence	End of the Cold War, Thatcherism, fall of the Berlin Wall, Gorbachev/Reagan era, "latch-key kids," first PCs, dawn of mobile tech	9/11 attacks, social media, PlayStation, reality TV, Google Earth, Iraq invasion, music festivals	Global recession, mobile devices, climate change, energy crisis, globalization, user-generated content, Arab Spring, cloud computing, WikiLeaks
Aspirations	Home ownership	Job security	Work-life balance	Flexibility and freedom	Security and stability
Attitude to technology	Less relevant	Early adopters	Digital immigrants	Largely independent of technology	"Technocholics" – totally dependent on IT
Signature product	Automobile	Television	Personal computer	Tablet / smartphone	Google Glass, graphene, nanotechnology, 3-D printing, driverless cars
Main communication medium	Formal letter	Telephone	E-mail & SMS	SMS or social media	Wearable or handheld communication device
Communication style	Direct contact (face-to-face))	Direct (face-to-face); e-mail or phone acceptable	SMS or e-mail	Online & mobile (text messages)	Face-to-face via a mobile device
Preferred approach to financial decisions	Face-to-face meeting	Face-to-face preferred, though increasingly willing to go online	Online if time allows, otherwise face-to-face	Prefers an in-person meeting	Relies on friends' experiences to choose the optimal solution

Source: Marketingteacher, n.d.; author's adaptation.

Generation X – This cohort comprises consumers born in the second half of the 20th century. In Poland the usual range is c. 1961–1983; they are also called the PRL Generation or the “Nothing-Is-Serious” Generation. They often reject the marketing-created world and live without clear authorities, feeling “left out” by history because no major historical events marked their youth (Wikipedia, n.d.). The generation is noted for immense dedication to work and frequently puts it first; although it disdains the classic “rat race” and increasingly values work-life balance, the cult of work still distinguishes it most (businessinsider, n.d.). Scholars portray Generation X as a society unsure of its direction, people lost in the chaos of modernity and fashions; the symbol X signifies the unknown. What once signalled membership was a non-chalant lifestyle and blandness rather than faith or education. Those focused mainly on consumerism or immersed in corporate “rat races” do not truly belong to this group (Rybcieńska, 2016, n.d.).

Generation Y – Millennials. In Poland this generation includes people born roughly 1984 to 1997 (in countries such as the USA it is the 1980s- and 1990s-boom cohort). Other labels are the “Millennium Generation,” the “Digital Generation,” the “Next Generation,” and the “Flip-Flop and iPod Generation” (Wikipedia, n.d.). Raised in a free-market era, they have no memory of communism in Central-Eastern Europe or the Cold War (Generation Y in Poland does not remember the PRL era). Compared with Generation X, they quickly embraced new technology and are active users of digital media. With the internet—very familiar to them—they are said to live in a “global village.” They are highly educated, and quality of life and experiences matter more than ownership. Yet Millennials often live with parents longer than Gen X, delaying adulthood and independence. They display strong self-confidence, a conviction of uniqueness, a very high opinion of their abilities, a strong aversion to criticism, and inflated expectations (businessinsider, n.d.).

Generation Z – the Internet Generation, also called Generation C (for connect, communicate, change), the multitasking generation, the Silent Generation, or Generation @. In Poland it refers to those born after 1995 who are only now—or soon will be—entering the market, so descriptions remain cautious. One can merely indicate traits that are likely to shape their future market behavior (Wikipedia, n.d.).

“Z-ers” grew up in prosperity and new technologies, so they adapt easily to virtual worlds. They master the latest gadgets effortlessly, replacing real-world contacts with online ones. In essence, they live in a virtual world and belong to virtual communities built around shared

interests and passions. They are open-minded and may have several thousand Facebook friends spanning Europe, Brazil, India, China, and beyond.

Members of this cohort do not fear remote work; complex machines or software present no obstacle. Their core and greatest asset is fluency in the virtual world—knowing where to seek information or whom to ask, and doing so instantly. This lets them operate smoothly, without borders or limits. Another hallmark is effortless multitasking: they can track several auctions, chat, and watch a film simultaneously. They learn new apps in a flash and communicate boldly in foreign languages. Their openness makes what older generations deem risky a realm of fascination: they enjoy meeting new people, travelling, and have no qualms about working or interning on the “other side of the world” (Hysa, 2016, pp. 389–390).

A distinctive Polish feature of Generation Z is its pronounced internal diversity. The sense of a friendly world within reach does not hold for every Z-member. This cohort is the most economically, mentally, and culturally divided of all generations since World War II. Raised after 1989, it starkly reveals who was given a chance for better education, inherited wealth, and openness to the world—advantages that foster career success. Their parents—today’s forty-somethings—could seize the opportunities of Poland’s transition and free market; Z-ers “consume” those achievements but also feel their parents’ triumphs or failures. Experts stress that behavior is shaped not only by schooling but also by home culture—whether the household nurtured development, visited museums, read books, or travelled (Pawłowska, 2013, n.d.).

In the United States, 26 % of 16- to 19-year-olds (Generation Z) volunteer (Sparks & Honey, 2014). They are determined to change the world and believe they can. Their tech fluency lets them adapt swiftly to internet-centric industries—running fan pages, producing animations, designing websites, working in IT, online journalism, and PR. In careers they prize development opportunities, pay, and employer prestige; yet many will freelance, challenging the notion that one must leave home to work. “Going to work” seems nonsensical when tasks can be done on a tablet, smartphone, or laptop. Figure 3 shows how many work and learning-related activities they already carry out online. For Gen Z, teamwork does not require sharing a room. Foreign-language skills let them serve global clients found largely on the internet, which is where most contracts are sourced.

Z-ers are viewed as the most consumption-oriented generation, exposed to branding and advertising more than any previous cohort—even Millennials. Everyone must be reachable

not only on Facebook but also Snapchat, Instagram, YouTube, and often Twitter. For them, social-media presence is not a fad but essential for daily life; thus employers, universities, and favourite restaurants must be there if Z-ers are to identify with them (Jaworowicz, 2015, n.d.).

Figure 3. Generation Z online

Source: JWT Intelligence, 2012; Edudemic survey

Sociologists add that this cohort is often seen as a generation of only children—and of egoists. Born into prosperity, they were frequently the sole child because their parents focused on careers. To compensate for limited time together, parents indulged them, concentrating all attention on one youngster; as a result, many “Z-ers” are egocentric. They find it harder to forge lasting bonds and, accustomed to the comfortable life enjoyed under their parents’ roof, they tend to assume that everything simply “comes with the territory.”

According to Sparks & Honey (2014), young Generation Z consumers stand out for:

- **Short attention spans.** In 2000 the average person concentrated on an ad for about 12 seconds; today it is only 8 seconds. Gen Z consumes information in tiny blocks. Research suggests their brains have adapted to process vast amounts of data in very short bursts (Sparks & Honey, 2014). Winning—and holding—their attention is therefore a major challenge. They expect a solution before they even recognize the problem, value their time highly, and want specs for the newest phone before they voice any wish to buy it.

- **Image and video-based communication.** Gen Z follows the rule TLDR (“Too Long; Didn’t Read”). Brands understand this, so they craft content built on video, memes, or standalone images (Sparks & Honey, 2014).

Figure 4. Decline in Generation Z presence on Facebook

Source: Sparks & Honey, 2013

In 2014, 25 % of teenagers aged 13–17 left Facebook for Instagram (Figures 4 and 5). As this shows, young people also value their privacy: they prefer a medium where they can stay somewhat anonymous and where messages or party videos vanish after ten seconds or within twenty-four hours (Instagram Stories / Snapchat). Overall, 17 % of youths and children aged 8–16 admit they use a smartphone specifically to keep their activities private, since parents cannot see the device. Snapchat—still somewhat underrated in the Polish market—is this generation’s favourite medium; it meets the needs listed above while offering creativity and, simultaneously, private viewing. Consequently, the best channels for posting concise, engaging video content are YouTube and, increasingly, Snapchat. Instagram, however, remains the leader for photos (Sparks & Honey, 2014).

Figure 5. Growth in Generation Z presence on Instagram

Source: Sparks & Honey, 2013

- **Addiction to social media, coupled with a concern for privacy.** Unlike Generation Y—whose early social-media use often ignored privacy safeguards—Gen Z knows that impulsive digital acts may boost short-term visibility yet damage long-term career prospects. They are fully aware that whatever appears online “stays forever,” so they tailor each message to the specific platform.
- **“Consumption”** of information via mobile. Young people do not own—and are unlikely ever to own—television sets. They consume content chiefly on mobile devices, while printed newspapers strike them as truly archaic. For “Z-ers,” quality and authenticity of published material are crucial. Trust in the press—and even in bloggers—has fallen, partly because of product placement.
- **Creativity.** Generation Z wants to be perceived as creative and to gain online fame, so spaces for self-expression are vital. The term YUCCIE (Young Urban Creatives) was coined for young city-dwellers who keep pace with the digital world, design clothes, shoot videos, or even craft bespoke skins for their avatars. They yearn to stand out and be recognized as creative; therefore brands can profit by amplifying their work—promoting their package designs or films, or letting them create a personal T-shirt collection (Wikipedia, n.d.).

- **Unisex** as a leading fashion trend. Gender neutrality and individual style matter far more than traditional male–female divisions. Analysts stress that companies targeting this emoji-, hashtag-, and six-second-Vine-accustomed cohort must communicate as much as possible in a few words and the shortest time if they hope to capture its attention (Sparks & Honey, 2014).

In sum. Given these traits, Gen Z communication should be short, catchy, digitised, and chiefly video- or graphic-based. Any innovative channel built on new technology can succeed, because this cohort readily assimilates tech novelties. Crucially, messages must not feel intrusive; they should engage young audiences in ways that let them showcase their creativity and uniqueness.

2. Characteristics of mobile applications as a communication tool

2.1 Technologies used in mobile communication

The development of information technology enables consumers and enterprises to use a variety of mobile technologies and devices to communicate with their environment, as illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Technologies enabling communication tools to operate
Source: author's own elaboration

Bluetooth is now the standard short-range wireless-communication technology for virtually all electronic devices—computers, laptops, tablets, smartphones, keyboards, headsets, and other mobile gear—allowing connections at distances of up to 100 metres. On this basis Bluetooth marketing arose: advertising messages are delivered to nearby recipients via the Bluetooth protocol. This belongs to the broader concept of permission marketing—building and maintaining customer relationships with the person's consent to receive marketing content (the term also covers e-mail marketing such as newsletters) (Wikipedia, n.d.). A Bluetooth transmitter scans for devices in range, requests permission to send a message, and, once accepted, displays the media content. The main drawback is distance: reception is limited to the immediate vicinity (Technologie mobilne w marketingu, poradnikprzedsiębiorcy, 2016).

Bluetooth is, however, ideal for “wearables”—on-body electronics such as a smartphone paired with a smart-watch or smart clothing (Wikipedia, n.d.). Other uses include the smart home, where Bluetooth can control heating systems, LED lighting, and other household devices (Daszkiewicz & Eggeling, 2015). All of this forms part of the Internet of Things—equipping physical objects with electronics, software, and sensors (Wikipedia, n.d.).

Wi-Fi refers to the set of standards used to build wireless computer networks, especially local area networks (LAN) based on radio WLAN links. Range spans from a few metres to several kilometres. A wireless network links a group of computers that exchange data. In marketing there is also Wi-Fi marketing, used mainly by businesses visited daily by customers: as soon as a person logs in, the company can show a marketing message, redirect to its website, landing page, Facebook profile, or mobile app. After the visitor leaves the premises, the firm can still employ the captured data for remarketing, Facebook ads, or e-mail campaigns (Trojnar, 2015).

GSM (Global System for Mobile Communications) is the world's best-known mobile-phone standard, providing voice, data, and multimedia/text messaging. Strictly, GSM denotes the 2G network standard, but in common parlance the acronym covers the full family of mobile-network generations, notably (Ct.elhurt, n.d.):

- **2G (2nd Generation)** – the first fully digital mobile network, launched in 1991. Its advantage is near-universal availability; its weakness is low speed—about 50 kb/s (later upgraded to 1 Mb/s), practically unusable for modern Internet access. Owing to these limits and the rise of 3G, 2G is being phased out.
- **3G (3rd Generation)** – introduced in Japan in 2001, it offered unlimited Internet access for the first time. Initial speeds were 14 Mb/s, later 28 Mb/s. Compared with 2G, coverage and speed are far higher: for example, 3G now reaches about 90 % of Poland's territory and nearly 99 % of its population.
- **4G (4th Generation) / LTE** – the standard most heavily promoted by carriers. First launched commercially in Scandinavia in 2009, it delivers data rates often unattainable on fixed lines—up to 300 Mb/s theoretically, though actual speeds vary. 4G clearly provides the fastest, highest-quality mobile transfer today. LTE (Long Term Evolution) is the specific data-transfer protocol that runs on 4G. In Poland LTE has become the norm, with hundreds of new transmitters added each year to extend fast mobile Internet (Dailyweb, 2018).
- **5G (5th Generation)** – the newest, still-emerging standard. A preliminary ITU specification states that latency will not exceed 5 ms, upstream speeds will be about 10 Gb/s, and downstream 20 Gb/s. At Mobile World Congress (Barcelona, February 2017) a

Deutsche Telekom executive predicted that, as 5G and the Internet of Things proliferate (especially across whole cities), smartphones could even disappear. The first commercial 5G deployment occurred on 9 February 2018 at the Winter Olympics in South Korea. On 2 March 2018 the European Commission ruled that all EU member states must free the 700 MHz band for 5G by 2020; details are in the 5G PPP (Public-Private Partnership) roadmap (M. Usidus, n.d.). The goal is to supply the communications infrastructure for next-generation mobile apps that link devices to smart objects (Internet of Things). Software virtualisation will enable innovative business models across many sectors—transport, manufacturing, logistics, energy, healthcare, media, entertainment. New virtual mobile services critical to the economy and society are envisaged, from virtual reality and remote work to online health monitoring, smart cars, drone deliveries, and autonomous pilots (European Commission, 2018).

For mobile apps that work offline and do not use geolocation, wireless-Internet speed is irrelevant. But if an app relies on geolocation and continuous connectivity—such as Pokémon Go, which uses augmented reality—then widespread, fast Internet access is crucial. Looking ahead, the 5G standard will be pivotal: once deployed, data will flow at lightning speed, allowing always-online applications to further improve their performance.

2.2 Features, scope of use, and design principles of mobile applications

The primary tools used in mobile communication via the Internet are mobile websites and applications.

The most important feature of a **mobile website** is that it can display correctly on mobile devices with different screen sizes, provided the device has network access. A mobile site usually supplements the desktop version and is one of the basic instruments of mobile marketing. When viewed on a mobile device, such a site serves mainly an informational purpose; extended functionality is typically provided in a dedicated mobile app.

A good example is the mobile website of Reserved, a Polish clothing brand. On this site, customers can: locate brick-and-mortar stores, browse current collections, and access a library of ready-made outfits figure 7 (Sadowska 2013, pp. 124–125).

Figure 7. Responsive mobile website

Source: Reserved mobile site, 2018; author's own elaboration.

A **mobile application** is software that runs on portable mobile devices such as smartphones, tablets, palmtops and feature phones (Wikipedia, n.d.). As a tool of innovative

mobile marketing, mobile apps offer wide-ranging capabilities and can ultimately help acquire new customers, raise brand awareness among consumers and, in turn, generate tangible revenue growth (Jasiulewicz 2015, pp. 317–320).

Mobile apps can be classified either by purpose or by the way they are built. In the latter case three groups are distinguished: web apps, native apps and hybrid apps.

- Web apps operate through a browser; in practice they are the mobile websites discussed earlier. Examples include Allegro, Wikipedia and Jakdojade.pl.
- Native apps are developed for a specific platform—iOS, Android or Windows Phone. Their chief advantages are high performance and unrestricted access to device components such as GPS, an accelerometer and a gyroscope.
 - GPS enables geolocation, allowing the geographical position of people or objects to be identified, the best offer to be matched and the nearest bricks-and-mortar outlet to be found (Wolniewicz, n.d.).
 - The accelerometer detects the device’s orientation, permitting the screen image to rotate automatically.
 - The gyroscope determines the handset’s position on the X, Y and Z axes, letting users control functions simply by moving the phone. Gyroscopes work best in games, VR apps and for camera image stabilisation (tech.wp, n.d.).
- Hybrid apps combine features of web and native solutions, though they rely mainly on web technologies. They integrate easily with websites, yet run more slowly and enjoy less hardware access than native apps—though more than pure web apps (Róg, n.d.).

Using a mobile app is far easier and more intuitive than browsing the mobile web, which explains their surge in popularity in recent years. A smartphone accompanies today’s consumer everywhere, enabling immediate access to services or payments with a single tap. The trend is fuelled by the spread of high-speed mobile Internet, discussed in the previous subsection.

In July 2016 mobile devices (smartphones and tablets) accounted for more than 50 % of total time spent online (Figure 5). Tablets, laptops and desktop computers will, of course, remain in use, but their role in communication will decline in the coming years. Publishers and advertisers should therefore factor this shift into their online marketing strategies. ComScore data show the share of Internet consumption measured by time spent across devices and platforms—computers, tablets and, crucially, smartphones (Lella 2016).

Table 3. Programming languages used to develop mobile applications

Technology	Logo	Description
Java		The Android operating system is written in Java, which makes the language a leader here: an app created in Java is compatible with every Android version. Java can be used for Android apps, web applications, servers, Big Data tools, and games.
Python		Python is a very mature yet easy-to-learn, readable language. It can be used to build Android apps as well as desktop software from scratch. Notable examples include Spotify, the mobile game World of Tanks, Instagram, and YouTube.
Swift		Released by Apple Inc. in June 2014 for iOS (and supporting systems) and Linux, Swift is the primary language for developing iOS and macOS apps. It is one of the fastest-growing technologies.
PHP		An open, server-side scripting language created by Zend Technologies in 1995. Originally designed for websites, it is now used for general development. While mainly intended for dynamic web pages, Zend notes that PHP can also be used to build Android and iOS apps. Sites such as Facebook, Wikipedia, Flickr, Yahoo, and Tumblr run on PHP.
C#		A general-purpose language developed by Microsoft. C# can be used for almost anything—from server applications and web services to games and mobile apps. It is a top choice for mobile games because the Unity 3D engine (for creating 2-D/3-D games and interactive content) supports it.
Objective-C		An object-oriented, general-purpose language derived from C. Objective-C was Apple’s main language for iOS and macOS before Swift, and it remains a top option because all types of apps can still be created in it.
C++		C++ extends C. It is highly versatile: many mobile apps in finance, banking, manufacturing, and gaming are built with it. C++ lets developers code for Android, Windows, and iOS. Major tools such as Google Chrome, Amazon’s backend, PayPal, World of Warcraft, and Photoshop were also created in C++.
Ruby		Ruby is a general, object-oriented language developed by Yukihiro “Matz” Matsumoto in the 1990s. Although simple, it requires a framework like RubyMotion or Rhodes to produce Android, iOS, Windows, or macOS apps. Well-known sites built with Ruby include Fiverr, Airbnb, Pixlr, Groupon, Basecamp, Scribd, Bloomberg, and ThemeForest.

Source: Buildfire, n.d.

Table 3 lists selected programming languages for mobile applications. It shows that the best technological choice for developing augmented- or virtual-reality software is C# or its extension C++. Both languages are supported by Unity 3D, which enables the creation of two-dimensional and—more importantly—three-dimensional visualisations that form the backbone of VR and AR apps. A further advantage is the technology’s flexibility: it lets developers build applications for Android, iOS, and Windows platforms.

Czas spędzany w internecie wg urządzeń i platform (lipiec 2016):

- **smartfony:**
 - aplikacje mobilne: 50%
 - strony mobilne: 7%
- **tablety:**
 - aplikacje mobilne: 9%
 - strony WWW: 2%
- **komputery i laptopy:** 32%

Figure 8. Time spent on the Internet by device and platform in the United States (July 2016)
Source: comScore, 2016

Mobile applications are revolutionising both consumption itself and the material available on the Internet—referred to in marketing jargon as content. Recipients of mobile content are increasingly called mobilenauts, with Generation Z forming the core of this group. Figure 9 shows the time users spend online, broken down by age and by the device used for “consuming” the Internet.

Key observations:

- Among the oldest members of Generation Z, fully 66 % of online time is spent in mobile apps on a smartphone—and the younger the cohort, the higher that share.
- Mobile websites account for only 7 % of smartphone Internet time, while the personal computer represents 23 %.
- Users aged 25–65 also favour the smartphone, but their reliance on computers rises steadily with age.
- Consumers over 65 spend most of their Internet time on a computer (53 %), with the smartphone making up just 27 %.

Figure 9. Time spent on devices by age group

Source:

ComScore,

2017

Figure 10. Time spent online via mobile apps in the United States (2014 – 2016)

Source: comScore, 2016

Meanwhile, Figure 10 shows the change in time spent in apps between 2014 and 2016. This may be due primarily to the widespread adoption of smartphones over the past few years and to users beginning to use a smartphone at ever younger ages (Mobirank, n.d.).

In mobile applications, beyond high-quality code, a more important element is the concept of **User Experience (UX)**—the user’s impressions when interacting with an interactive product. Designing UX involves crafting interactive products in a way that is as optimized as possible for the user’s needs (Wikipedia, n.d.). An app should above all meet the following criteria: functionality, usability and ergonomics:

Functionality means the mobile product should be optimized for ease of use. Core features should be very easily accessible and intuitive. A mobile app must satisfy the user’s needs in the most efficient way possible. Too many secondary features can dilute the core problem-solving function the product provides. It is important that features do not cannibalize each other and that the primary purpose of the app remains its strongest selling point—the reason users will download it. If too many features have been proposed and some must be cut, the recommended tool is a “value-cost matrix,” the simplest way to estimate the initial project scope. It lets you verify the order in which functions should be implemented (Samsel, 2017, n.d.).

Usability is another crucial evaluation criterion. Apps are used not only on the couch at home but also in less-ideal settings—on a crowded tram, on a sunny park bench, or while walking. The context in which a smartphone is used is essential when you consider the physical characteristics of modern screens. Screen diagonals and pixel densities on today’s devices are increasing. It becomes very difficult to use apps on a modern phone with a 5-inch screen while riding a crowded tram with only one hand free. Performing basic actions—like tapping the “hamburger” menu—is often impossible, since that control is typically placed in the upper-left or upper-right corner (see Figure 11). With current screen sizes, these corners are almost unreachable by right-handed users, who make up about 85–92 % of the population (Samsel, 2017, n.d.)

Figure 11. How the way a mobile device is held translates into interface-use efficiency

Source: Lukew, 2015.

The fundamental requirement for a mobile application is the ergonomic handling of gestures—not only finger movements on the screen but also actions like properly shaking the device or changing its orientation. Implementing standard gestures—taps, swipes, pinches—poses no difficulty for users because the effect of each gesture is clear and intuitive. To introduce non-standard gestures, however, you must first teach users how to perform them. For example, double tapping in the Instagram app automatically “likes” a photo. Another example is swiping profile photos in Tinder to like (swipe right) or reject (swipe left) a user. By analyzing which gestures a user group is already familiar with, you can optimize interaction efficiency; poorly chosen gestures may have the opposite effect. Figure 12 illustrates the most popular gestures recognized by mobile applications (Samsel, 2017). These gestures are also used in augmented-reality (AR) apps.

Figure 12. Most popular gestures recognized by mobile applications

Source: (Lukew, 2010)

Mobile applications have become an indispensable element of communication in today's world, not only between users but also between clients and businesses. The adoption of apps positively contributes to shaping the image of a modern twenty-first-century brand. Using this tool enables two-way communication, which is highly valued by contemporary customers and is gradually becoming a requirement.

2.3 Characteristics of Selected Mobile Applications in VR and AR Technology

An example of using augmented reality in education is the application **"Anatomy 4D"** which in a highly engaging way demonstrates the possibilities and potential of this technology. For the app to work, you need the appropriate printout (available for download from the software manufacturer's website), which you then print, launch the application, and point your device's camera at the paper. The sheets appear to come alive, revealing three-dimensional scientific models that can be viewed from every angle (Figure 13). It's worth noting that the models are scalable—bringing the camera closer to the paper enlarges the virtual image. The app also allows users to connect and disconnect model layers, which greatly aids student

learning. For example, in the human body model you can hide the muscles and all other systems to see only the skeleton. In the heart model, you can turn off the atria to examine the paths of the major arteries (Komputerswiat, 2017).

Figure 13. AR mobile application “Anatomy 4D”

Source: author’s own elaboration, 2018.

Meanwhile, the entertainment industry’s favorite became the mobile game Pokémon Go, which was released in July 2016 by Niantic. It was met with very positive reception from both younger and older mobile gamers. The game allowed players to collect creatures from the Japanese cartoon in the real world, effectively stepping into the role of the show’s protagonist. It used components such as the device’s camera and GPS module to “catch” Pokémon appearing on the screen. After creating an avatar in their own likeness, the user was located on a world map via GPS. The in-app map corresponds to real-world geography, and virtual objects—such as battle gyms, PokéStops, or the Pokémon themselves—become active only when the player is physically near them. Interestingly, these locations were often random, but sometimes a nearby local business would leverage the influx of players to attract new customers. The app also offers purchasable items that can draw rare virtual Pokémon for a

limited time—a feature local businesses likewise used to entice visitors. The game’s mechanics encourage users to move through the real world to achieve satisfying results in the virtual game. At its peak, more than 28 million users logged in daily (cinemablend, n.d.).

Figure 14. Pokémon Go – the most popular AR game

Source: (komputerswiat.pl, 2017)

An application that in the future may greatly ease people’s lives—and even replace them in roles requiring foreign-language skills—is Google Translate. It can not only translate text typed via the keyboard or from voice recordings, but also text on a page in real time. After selecting the language you want to translate from, simply point your device’s camera at a sign, label, or sheet of paper, and all the contained text will be rendered in your chosen target language (Zimowska, 2017, n.d.).

Figure 15. Google Translate in AR technology

Source: (Komputerswiat.pl, 2017)

User experience in VR applications is still in its early stages and continues to develop dynamically. The main challenge is that users are accustomed to 2D navigation, while 3D is entirely new to them. To use virtual-reality apps, you primarily need a headset—into which you insert a smartphone—and navigation is driven by head movement, though a Bluetooth controller can also assist. Below are UX best practices for VR apps:

- Gaze targeting – All interactions between the user and the app are performed by the user looking at a given element. For these interactions to succeed, the system must accurately infer the user’s true intent, avoiding errors and optimizing in-app navigation as much

as possible.

Figure 16. Optimal size of objects at a distance of 2 meters

Source: (Microsoft.com, 2018)

To further simplify navigation through this technology, a “Cursor Gaze” is introduced, which lets the user know exactly what they are looking at and which element they are interacting with, as shown in Figure 15; additionally, a gesture can be added to enable the user to interact with the application (Microsoft, 2018).

Figure 16. Example of highlighting an object by focusing gaze on it

Source: (Microsoft.com, 2018)

- *Voice design* – Gaze, gesture, and voice form the fundamental communication channels. Gaze combined with a cursor serves to locate the content the user wants to interact with, while a gesture or voice command can be used to complete that interaction. When designing VR applications, it’s essential to optimize all of these UX tools so they work harmoniously together. Voice is a very powerful and convenient way to control the system and app. Given the variety of accents, dialects, and other speech variations, it’s important to choose

keywords carefully so that user commands are always interpreted unambiguously. Figure 17 shows an example of the app prompting the user to confirm a selected interaction (Microsoft, 2018).

Figure 17. Example of “look-and-say” navigation

Source: (Microsoft.com, 2018)

- *Spatial sound* – more precisely “spatial audio,” serves as a navigation aid by immersing the user in the surrounding virtual environment. By more closely reproducing real-world soundscapes—whether for simple tasks like locating objects, capturing attention, or gaining a deeper understanding of one’s surroundings—it helps blur the boundary between the real and virtual worlds. The more an app’s audio mimics real life, the less distinction the user perceives between the two (Microsoft, 2018).

The first VR application to showcase this is “Titans of Space” (Figure 18). On a “journey” through the solar system, the user can learn facts about each planet they visit. When you insert your smartphone into a VR headset, you’re transported to a spacecraft you control with head movements, thanks to the gaze-targeting mechanism described above.

Figure 18. Travel mode in the “Titans of Space VR” application

Source: author’s own elaboration, 2018.

Another example of virtual reality in the entertainment industry is the smartphone VR game “Lost In The Kismet – VR Escape” (Figure 19), where simple controls rely primarily on looking around and solving logic puzzles. Players enjoy an escape-room experience in VR using only their phone and a headset. Without touching the screen—using gaze targeting—they fixate on objects to solve riddles that bring them closer to escaping the room.

Figure 19. Game mode in the “Lost in the Kismet VR” application

Source: author’s own elaboration, 2018.

Figure 20. Main menu in the “Public Speaking VR” application

Source: author’s own elaboration, 2018.

Psychologists and educational centers can employ virtual reality in therapy, since this technology can recreate stressful situations for patients—such as standing atop a skyscraper to confront acrophobia, encountering a spider, or facing the fear of public speaking. One such application is Public Speaking VR, which places the user before an audience or in a high-stakes business meeting they must lead. This setup allows users to rehearse presentations in near-real conditions, helping them acclimate to stress and refine their performance (Zimowska, 2017, n.d.).

The growth dynamics of AR and VR also reflect ongoing work by tech giants like Google and Apple to enhance their development frameworks, some of which have already been released. As these technologies and frameworks mature, the number of applications—and therefore users—will rise, as illustrated in Figure 21. In particular, the gaming segment is projected to add the most users, reaching 216 million worldwide by 2025.

These technologies offer enormous opportunities for both established firms and new entrants. According to Statista (Figure 22), the AR and VR market is expected to reach USD 215 billion by 2021. This growth will be driven largely by major tech companies’ involvement and by the provision of appropriate tools, underlining the industry’s significant market potential and ease of expansion (newgenapps, 2018).

Figure 21. Investments in AR/VR projects from 2012 to Q2 2016

Source: (Cbinsights.com, 2016)

Figure 22. Forecast of the global augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) market from 2016 to 2021 (in USD billions)

Source: Statista.com, 2018

The virtual and augmented reality market is still developing, which makes it difficult to determine its exact value. However, forecasts for these technologies are very optimistic. Since the beginning of 2016, \$1.3 billion has been invested in projects related to this industry across 76 transactions, according to CBInsights (Alferov, 2016).

3. Evaluation of Mobile Applications as a Communication Tool in the Light of a Usability Test

3.1 Research Methodology

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the usability of VR and AR applications as perceived by Generation Z users. Usability was operationalized in terms of task-completion ease (effectiveness) and the number of errors (obstacles) encountered while attempting each task. A further aim was to identify which interface elements most strongly captured participants' attention.

In May 2018 we carried out a structured usability test (UX testing). This method diagnoses weaknesses in a web service or mobile app by observing real-time interactions between users and the product. Its overarching goal is to refine the virtual product's navigation, visual design, and information architecture (Kaczmarek, 2016, pp. 102–103).

Applying usability testing to mobile applications enables us to:

- Identify inconsistencies and design issues in interface usability and content. Potential sources of problems include (Usability.gov, n.d.):
 - Navigation errors: failures to locate the correct functionality, excessive tapping to complete a process, or deviation from the recommended navigation flow.
 - Presentation errors: inability to locate or extract desired information, or incorrect selections caused by ambiguous labeling.
 - Interaction errors: misuse of toolbars or functions, or difficulties with home/exit screens.
- Collect controlled, representative data that reveal the app's weak points and inform more effective design solutions.
- Determine the performance levels users expect from the application.

A purposive sample of four Generation Z individuals (ages 17–21) was recruited; none had prior experience with the tested apps. Each participant received 2–3 scenario-based tasks per application. VR headsets were used for VR apps, and a smartphone was used for AR and other tests.

Participants tested the four applications profiled in Chapter 2 and completed the following tasks:

- Anatomy 4D

1. You are preparing for an anatomy class and wish to view what lies immediately beneath the skin of the displayed model.
 2. The model defaults to female anatomy; change it to male anatomy.
 3. Zoom in on specific organs and tissues—adjust the model’s scale to examine details more closely.
- Google Translate
 1. At lunch with a foreign colleague, translate a Polish menu item into English in the shortest possible time using real-time translation.
 2. While on holiday in the USA, you must sign a car-rental agreement but cannot understand one sentence. Translate that excerpt from English into Polish by photographing and highlighting only the unclear portion.
 - Titans of Space
 1. Launch the app, imagine you are piloting a spacecraft, and enter “travel mode” to journey through the solar system.
 2. You arrive at a planet of interest—locate and review its informational overlay.
 3. Initiate travel to the next planet to continue your exploration.
 - Lost in the Kismet – VR Escape
 1. You find yourself trapped in a room and must solve a puzzle to progress to the next level—complete the challenge and advance.
 2. A series of riddles blocks your path—identify the solutions and escape the room.

During each test session, participants used the “thinking aloud” technique, verbalizing their impressions and difficulties. Upon completion, they filled out a brief questionnaire rating each app on: Innovativeness, User-Experience design, User-Interface design, Educational value, Entertainment value and attention engagement.

Detailed task-performance metrics for each application are presented in the thesis appendix.

3.2 Evaluation of AR Technology Applications

The AR-based mobile applications selected for evaluation were, in sequence, Anatomy 4D and Google Translate.

Evaluation of the “Anatomy 4D” Application

Based on the completed tasks, participants judged the application to be highly innovative and engaging, but saw it as only suitable for occasional use—given that most users have no ongoing need to study human anatomy.

When performing the first task (revealing what lies beneath the model’s skin), all participants looked for controls in the menu at the lower-right corner. By trial and error they sought the function that would expose the underlying structures. Time to complete this task ranged from 45 seconds to 2 minutes 25 seconds. None noticed the menu in the upper-left corner; the bottom menu was always their first choice.

The gender-swap task was completed without any issues. All participants had already discovered that function during the first task, so they executed it effortlessly.

For the third task—resizing the model—some testers initially assumed that the slider in the upper-right corner controlled zoom. Once they realised that a pinch gesture was required, they agreed that the pinch was the most intuitive way to scale the model.

All participants rated the application’s navigation and overall intuitiveness as excellent, a finding supported by both their task-success rates and their think-aloud comments. They were less unanimous about the graphics, however, flagging visual quality as an area for improvement. One tester even suggested adding a skin-color selector. All agreed that the app would be especially useful for students in anatomy courses or as an engaging alternative learning tool. Half proposed adding the ability to zoom in on each organ with a descriptive overlay—an enhancement they felt would significantly deepen their understanding.

In summary, the study highlighted graphics and model-render quality as the primary areas to address. Users also desired more manipulation features—such as an animation mode to see the model in motion—and greater educational depth. While the app clearly showcases

AR's potential, enriching it with organ-specific descriptions and independent selection would deliver genuine added value to its users.

Evaluation of the “Google Translate” Application

Based on the tasks performed, testers found the app useful and beneficial for everyday use, especially when abroad. The primary advantage of the real-time translation feature is its speed, as unanimously noted by all participants. The app's biggest drawback is the quality of its translations. During the Polish-to-English translation task, testers observed that the live translation renders only word-by-word equivalents rather than full sentences. This approach significantly hinders complete comprehension due to its disregard for grammatical structure. Task completion times ranged from 30 seconds to two minutes, yet all participants confirmed they could grasp the sentence's meaning despite the subpar translation.

Testers differed in their assessment of Google Translate's navigation and intuitiveness—only some rated these aspects very highly and had no trouble accessing the AR real-time translation functions. One participant suggested UX enhancements to make those features more visible.

Several users struggled with the second task—translating a fragment by photographing and selecting only the unclear portion—because they were unaware of the function for translating a marked text segment. All testers agreed that image-based translation is more precise and produces higher-quality results.

Participants considered the app's visual design appropriate and in need of no changes. However, the study identified navigation as the top area for improvement: available functions should be more prominently displayed. It was recommended to add tooltips or guided prompts to introduce new users to each feature. Finally, testers concurred that real-time translation quality requires enhancement, as some outputs were nonsensical; translations improved when the camera was held on the text for a longer duration.

3.3 Evaluation of VR Technology Applications

Participants in the study evaluated, in sequence, the following VR mobile applications: Titans of Space and Lost In The Kismet – VR Escape.

Evaluation of the “Titans of Space” application

All participants who tested the application described the experience as highly educational, revealing the potential of modern technology. Initially, users faced difficulties with orientation and navigating the virtual environment. However, gaze targeting was universally rated as a very intuitive method of interaction within the VR application. Some noted that this form of control only became intuitive after a short period of use. The initial disorientation stemmed from participants' lack of prior exposure to VR technology, but as the study demonstrated, they quickly adapted. This confirms that gaze targeting is both intuitive and easily adoptable by the younger generation. Several users suggested that the application could include an introductory animation to demonstrate how to navigate using eye movement.

The average time to complete the first task—activating travel mode—ranged from 30 seconds to 1 minute and 30 seconds. All participants completed this task without issues, with a smooth transition from launching the app to entering gameplay. Some participants, intrigued by the experience, explored additional features beyond those required in the usability test.

For the second task—finding additional information about the currently visited planet—most users instinctively clicked the “i” button, finding it highly intuitive. This task was completed within 10 to 15 seconds.

One participant highlighted the background music as a particularly important feature, as it enhanced the sense of immersion and the mood for space exploration. However, all users agreed that the application could become monotonous quickly. They suggested enriching the experience with features such as a simulation of Earth's formation or flying through an asteroid field.

A common critique concerned the graphical quality of the spaceship, which noticeably underperformed compared to the visuals of outer space. Additionally, users with vision impairments reported eye fatigue caused by using the headset. More broadly, eye strain from prolonged use emerged as a key area in need of improvement in VR applications.

Evaluation of the “Lost in the Kismet” Application

All participants testing the application were highly engaged with it. Nearly every respondent fully "immersed" themselves in the virtual environment and the scenario their character was experiencing. Gaze targeting and Cursor gaze were generally rated positively by the participants as highly intuitive control mechanisms. However, one participant noted that the controls felt too slow, which led to frustration due to the inability to maneuver quickly within the game. The most praised feature of the application was its core game concept, which deeply absorbed the users. The introductory task, aimed at familiarizing users with the application's mechanics and control methods, was completed in a range of 30 seconds to 1 minute and 50 seconds.

The second task—completing the entire game—proved challenging enough that one participant quit after five minutes due to eye strain caused by prolonged VR use. Nevertheless, completion of the second task did not exceed 11 minutes for the others.

In the opinion of the participants, the first level—being very simple—was a well-designed tutorial that helped users understand how the application worked. One participant, after completing the full game, stated that she would be willing to purchase additional levels because she found the experience so engaging.

The application's main weakness was its graphics; all participants unanimously identified this as the top area needing improvement in terms of functionality and visual appeal.

The usability tests confirmed the strong potential of the VR gaming industry, as the technology allows for deep immersion in the virtual world and stimulates multiple senses during gameplay. However, the most significant drawback remains the intense visual strain caused by VR applications, which should be considered a key limitation of the technology.

Conclusion

Young consumers from Generation Z predominantly use smartphones, making mobile applications their primary communication channel and a key source of entertainment. They live in a virtual world and belong to virtual communities formed by individuals with shared interests and passions. Generation Z is highly adept in navigating the digital environment and efficiently searching for information. In the applications they use, this generation prefers brief, catchy, and non-intrusive messages, along with interactive experiences that allow them to express their uniqueness.

This study focused on applications utilizing augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) technologies, which were assessed through usability testing by representatives of Generation Z. The primary research objective was achieved: empirical evidence confirmed the hypothesis that VR technology has greater user engagement potential than AR. This conclusion was driven by factors such as entertainment value and attention absorption, which were rated higher in VR applications. VR apps were also perceived as more innovative. However, in terms of communication potential, AR technology proved more advantageous, mainly due to its ease of use. Unlike VR, which requires headsets, space, and significant time commitment due to its full-immersion nature, AR applications only require a smartphone and possibly a printed marker. This makes AR-based communication more dynamic—an attribute particularly valued by Generation Z. Additionally, AR apps scored higher in User Experience and User Interface design due to their reliance on familiar mobile gesture controls.

The study validated the hypothesis that gaze-based control mechanisms (Gaze Targeting) are particularly appealing to Generation Z. Although users initially experienced some difficulties, they quickly adapted and found this form of interaction highly intuitive.

On the other hand, the hypothesis that graphic design holds equal importance to navigation intuitiveness in AR and VR applications was not confirmed. For Generation Z users, visual aesthetics are often prioritized over intuitive navigation—especially in VR apps, where "poor graphics" were consistently cited as the main drawback.

The hypothesis that VR technology negatively affects human health, particularly visual function, was supported. Participants reported eye strain and discomfort during extended use of VR applications.

Generation Z consumers are highly active mobile app users. When it comes to emerging technologies integrated into mobile applications, they expect strong utility value—meaning access to a variety of functionalities. Apps must be both simple and intuitive while offering surprising depth and variety. For Generation Z, merely implementing AR or VR is not sufficient to ensure acceptance; a mobile application must also meet their high standards for design, usability, and innovation.

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List of Figures

Figure 1. Consumer behavior

Figure 2. Monthly active users (in millions) of the most popular mobile communication apps

Figure 3. Generation Z online

Figure 4. Decline in Generation Z presence on Facebook

Figure 5. Growth in Generation Z presence on Instagram

Figure 6. Technologies enabling communication tools to operate

Figure 7. Responsive mobile website

Figure 8. Time spent on the Internet by device and platform in the United States (July 2016)

Figure 9. Time spent on devices by age group

Figure 10. Time spent online via mobile apps in the United States (2014 – 2016)

Figure 11. How the way a mobile device is held translates into interface-use efficiency

Figure 12. Most popular gestures recognized by mobile applications

Figure 13. AR mobile application “Anatomy 4D”

Figure 14. Pokémon Go – the most popular AR game

Figure 15. Optimal size of objects at a distance of 2 meters

Figure 16. Example of highlighting an object by focusing gaze on it

Figure 17. Example of “look-and-say” navigation

Figure 18. Travel mode in the “Titans of Space VR” application

Figure 19. Game mode in the “Lost in the Kismet VR” application

Figure 20. Main menu in the “Public Speaking VR” application

Figure 21. Investments in AR/VR projects from 2012 to Q2 2016

Figure 22. Forecast of the global augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR) market from 2016 to 2021 (in USD billions)

List of Tables

Table 1. Key differences between the traditional consumer and the new-era consumer

Table 2. Differences Between Consumer Generations

Table 3. Programming languages used to develop mobile applications

Appendix

Appendix 1. Usability Test Results of VR and AR Applications

AR Application	Anatomy 4D					
Task	Task 1		Task 2		Task 3	
	You want to see what is under the skin of the displayed character.		The character in the application is female—please change the gender to male.		You would like to take a closer look at selected organs and tissues. Try changing the size of the displayed character.	
Person 1	<p>The user, when asked to change the level of skin intensity on the character's body, immediately navigated to the menu in the lower right corner, looking for an option to enable and disable the skin. After some time, unable to find the appropriate element responsible for the skin, the test facilitator suggested looking in a different menu. After 45 seconds, the user managed to find the function, and upon doing so admitted that it was a fairly logical solution and very interesting, as it allowed changing the "skin layers."</p>		<p>The user immediately changed the gender of the displayed character because they had already seen this function when attempting to complete the first task.</p>		<p>The tester automatically zoomed in and out on the character, stating that this feature is found in the vast majority of Android apps, so they assumed this one would work the same way.</p>	
Comments	<p>The user noted that the application definitely stands out compared to others. They stated that the control and navigation are done as well as possible for this type of app and that it couldn't be improved further. The main advantage, according to the user, is its ease of use and intuitive navigation. The interface design was rated as excellent; however, the user pointed out that the quality of the character model leaves much to be desired.</p> <p>The user missed having descriptions of individual organs in the app. Since they were not familiar with human anatomy but were theoretically interested in learning something, they said they wouldn't actually learn anything because the app did not include such information, and the printout provided only fun facts. They noted, however, that the app could be useful to diversify an anatomy lecture, although the instructor would need to describe the individual body parts, which could slow down the learning process.</p>					
Ocena	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	4	5	3	3	2	2
Person 2	<p>Within 50 seconds, the user changed the skin opacity level. Initially, they searched for the solution in the bottom-right menu and did not notice the slider in the top-right corner of the interface. After removing the muscles from the character, they considered the task complete. After a slight prompt from the researcher to</p>		<p>Through trial and error, the user changed the gender of the displayed character in about 20 seconds without major complications.</p>		<p>Zooming in and out of the figure occurred without any problems—the user intuitively used a pinch gesture to zoom out.</p>	

	explore other options in the app, the user began checking the slider's purpose. At first, they tried clicking it to make changes, but shortly realized that the slider could be dragged to make adjustments in the app interface.					
Comments	<p>The user felt the app was logical and very intuitive to use. The menu in the bottom right was very prominent and drew most of the user's attention. They initially thought the top-right slider was used to change the size of the figure. The first interaction with the app—where the character appeared on screen after pointing the camera at the printed card—left a strong impression and created a "wow" effect. The user appreciated the smooth interaction between the app and the printed page.</p> <p>The user suggested they would prefer the ability to view individual organs up close after clicking, instead of seeing everything at once. They added that after zooming in and clicking on a specific bone, it would be useful if a description of that body part appeared. The user believed the app would be a great tool for medical students and, if enriched with the above features, could serve as a very good learning alternative.</p>					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	4	4	4	3	3	3
Person 3	After 55 seconds, the user managed to change the opacity level of the skin displayed on the model, following a suggestion to look for a control option other than the bottom-right menu. The user automatically moved to the slider above and quickly understood its function without major issues.		The tester, without being read the instruction for Task 2 (changing the gender of the displayed avatar), completed it on their own while exploring the app and testing its features.		Again, without being read the instruction for Task 3, the user independently zoomed in and out on the displayed figure. They were highly curious and engaged while using the app.	
Comments	The tester suggested adding the ability to rotate the model and view it from the back, considering it a very useful feature. The most interesting functionality for the user was changing the skin opacity. While using the app, they rated the navigation very highly, emphasizing its intuitiveness. They argued that people familiar with smartphones would quickly adapt to the app, as common gestures like "pinch to zoom" are widely used in other applications. When evaluating the graphics, the user suggested possible improvements but acknowledged that the current quality is sufficient for this type of application. They believed that using such an app in elementary or middle school would greatly help students retain more from lessons.					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience Design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	5	5	5	5	2	3
Person 4	Launching the app triggered a "wow" effect for the user. After 1 minute and 45 seconds, the user removed the muscles, thinking they had changed the skin. After another 40 seconds and a prompt to look for a different menu, the user successfully changed the opacity level of the skin on the model.		After 5 seconds, the user changed the model's gender easily, thanks to a previous task approached through "trial and error," which helped them become familiar with the app.		The user tried to zoom in and out using the right-side slider—even though they had used it for a different function minutes earlier—because it seemed more intuitive for resizing the figure. After a prompt, the user immediately adjusted to using the "pinch" gesture to zoom in and out.	

Comments	The user expressed very positive initial impressions, saying they were surprised by the 3D model that appeared on the printed sheet. They suggested it would be a nice feature to change the model's skin color. The user rated the app as very modern and admitted that it was very easy to use, even though they initially overlooked the top-right slider. They had no complaints about the graphics or interface design. They also acknowledged that the app would be useful for those wanting to understand how the human body works. However, they did not find it particularly entertaining or educational, simply because the subject didn't interest them personally. Nonetheless, they rated the app's functionality very positively.					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience Design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	4	4	5	4	3	4
Google Translate						
Task	Task 1			Task 2		
	You're having lunch with a friend from abroad and want to translate a dish name from Polish to English as quickly as possible. Use the Google Translate app to do it in real time.			You're on vacation in the USA. You need to sign a car rental agreement but don't understand one sentence. Translate the specific part from English to Polish by taking a photo and highlighting only the unclear sentence.		
Person 1	The user, asked to translate text from English to Polish using the app in real time, found the feature and began the translation within 30 seconds, reading the translated text out loud. They admitted the translation quality was not very high and noted that one word wasn't translated at all. After trying to zoom in and out to get the word to register, the user gave up on translating it.			When asked to translate from Polish to English using a photo, the user took a picture and selected the correct part of the text within 40 seconds. They noted a big difference in translation quality compared to real-time translation.		
Comments	The tester pointed out that the app only translates individual words in real-time mode rather than full sentences, which often leads to inaccurate results. They acknowledged the speed of real-time translation as a strength, but the quality as a major drawback. They emphasized that the photo translation function was more useful due to its higher translation quality. The user rated navigation very highly, noting prior experience with Google Translate—though not with the real-time or photo features. Regarding the app's design, they said it was well done and hard to mess up. The tester said the app was interesting, but as someone not studying medicine, they wouldn't download it voluntarily—perhaps just out of curiosity, and would likely uninstall it shortly after.					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	3	5	5	2	1	3
Person 2	Within 20 seconds, the user—tasked with translating a fragment of text in real time from English to Polish—took a photo and waited for the app to respond. After the moderator pointed out that the task required real-time translation, the user returned to the main menu and began translating live. However, the default language setting was Polish-to-English, instead of English-to-Polish. After being prompted, the user switched the languages without any issues, completed the live translation, and read the translated text aloud.			When asked to translate a specific sentence from a whole page of text using a photo, the user had no trouble proceeding after taking the picture but struggled with highlighting the correct section. At first, they tapped individual words. After 30 seconds and a brief hint, they understood they had to "paint over" the entire sentence with a transparent marker for it to be translated.		
Comments	The user found the app useful, though the translation didn't always work perfectly. Still, they said that the meaning could usually be deduced. They felt the navigation could be clearer and					

	suggested that hints or tooltips would help. The app's graphic design and interface were considered sufficient for its type. The tester said they would definitely use this app on vacation in a foreign country—for example, to translate a restaurant menu.					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	4	4	5	4	3	4
Person 3	The user, asked to translate text from English to Polish in real time using the camera function, accessed the correct feature after 20 seconds but immediately took a photo instead of waiting for the text to be translated live on the screen. They noted that the constant changes in word meaning and font size made it difficult to read the correct translation. After stabilizing the camera, they read the translated text aloud.			When asked to translate text from Polish to English using a photo, the user took the photo immediately but didn't notice the need to highlight the text. They tried to move on to the next screen without selecting anything. After the moderator's instruction, the user highlighted the correct part of the text without difficulty. The translation missed a few words, making it inaccurate. After being asked to try again, the second attempt produced a translation that made enough sense to understand the sentence through deduction.		
Comments	The user acknowledged that the app would be very helpful while traveling abroad, for example when signing a room rental agreement during a trip. They admitted they would have trouble finding the real-time and photo translation functions due to poor visibility of those options, and would more likely type the words manually since they wouldn't know those features existed. The user also had difficulty highlighting the appropriate sentence fragment. They suggested improving the visual design and rearranging some buttons to make the app more intuitive. However, they concluded that the navigation is solid once a user becomes familiar with the app's features. The user noted that the app could be useful for language learning and suggested adding playful or gamified elements to make using it more enjoyable.					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	4	3	4	4	3	4
Person 4	After 30 seconds of being asked to use the camera to translate text from English to Polish, the user successfully activated the function. It created a "wow" effect — the user admitted they hadn't imagined that text could be translated in real time using a camera. Despite this, the app did not translate the text with enough precision; however, the tester said they could still understand the general meaning.			When translating text from Polish to English using the photo function, the user automatically switched the translation languages and almost immediately took a photo. Upon seeing the slightly darkened screen, they instinctively began "scribbling" over it to highlight the text. The user read the translation aloud and rated it as much more accurate than the first time.		
Comments	The user found the AR-based translation technology to be very modern and had no trouble navigating the app. They rated the interface as sufficiently simple and suitable for this type of application. While not finding it highly entertaining, they still described the experience as interesting and noted that the app could be helpful for learning a foreign language.					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	5	5	5	5	2	3
VR Application	Titans of Space					
Tasks	Task 1		Task 2		Task 3	
	Launch the Titans of Space app, imagine you are the pilot of a spaceship, and enter travel mode to begin a space journey.		You want to learn more about the planet you're currently near. Find additional information.		You want to travel to the next planet and continue exploring space. Begin the journey.	

Person 1	The user launched the application and entered travel mode within 50 seconds without major control issues.	After 10 seconds, the tester found the information button — the “i” symbol — and considered it highly intuitive.	In 20 more seconds, the user traveled to the next planet with no problems.			
Comments	The tester praised the concept of the app and suggested it could be used during lessons. They found the controls intuitive, although initially confusing in the menu. They recommended adding historical events (e.g., Earth's formation and evolution) to make the game less static. They also suggested adding realistic distances between planets to better convey the scale of the universe. The user noted it's more of a curiosity app and wouldn't use it for more than 10–15 minutes. They also mentioned that the graphics need improvement.					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	4	4	3	4	2	3
Person 2	At the start, the tester had difficulty orienting themselves in the 360-degree interface. They couldn't locate the menu or figure out how to navigate. After the facilitator explained that navigation was controlled solely by head movement, the user managed to enter game mode after 1 minute and 40 seconds.	Within 10 seconds, the tester easily found the "i" button with additional planet information.	After another 20 seconds, they successfully traveled to the next planet.			
Comments	<p>The app gave the user a “wow” effect, especially due to the travel perspective, the colors of the planets, and the planet info. However, the user missed having labeled constellations. They found the navigation insufficiently intuitive, which led to initial frustration due to a lack of instructions on how to control the spaceship — at one point, they tried to interact by blinking. Eventually, it became intuitive enough.</p> <p>The accompanying music was initially praised for creating an immersive atmosphere, but later became annoying. The tester suggested having different music for each planet. They also criticized the color scheme of the “pilot panel” buttons, calling them too bright and mismatched.</p> <p>After about 10 minutes of use, the user began complaining of eye strain. Despite this, they were very eager to explore the next planet because of how interestingly they were visually represented, with continuous rotation catching their attention.</p>					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	5	4	3	4	5	5
Person 3	The user, after 30 seconds of familiarizing themselves with the app, entered the game mode without major issues.	After 15 seconds, they found the “i” button on the control panel and accessed the information about the planet they were near.	Another 15 seconds later, the user traveled to the next planet without any problems.			
Comments	<p>The user felt like a spaceship pilot but noted that it would be helpful to have more controls, even in autopilot mode—something to interact with. They felt the ship should contain more “functional” technology. The journey itself was rated very positively. The control panel was eventually seen as intuitive, although there were initial issues navigating the app.</p> <p>The user believed the graphics need improvement, especially the spaceship's interior. They suggested the app could be used in geography classes to help students better visualize and understand the universe while having fun at the same time.</p>					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	5	3	3	4	5	5

Person 4	The user entered game mode after 38 seconds and immediately read the information displaying the ship's distance from the sun. Through trial and error, they quickly began navigating the spaceship and proceeded to travel to the next planet—Venus.	After 15 seconds, the user found the “i” button on the control panel and accessed information about the current planet.	After another 20 seconds, the user traveled to the next planet without any issues.			
Comments	<p>The user stated this was a new experience for them—“traveling” through space. They found the app’s controls to be very intuitive, noting that they immediately understood how it worked when the cursor started blinking, partly due to prior experience with VR apps. They felt the graphics could be improved but acknowledged that for people interested in space, the app could be a good alternative for learning.</p> <p>However, the user found the app a bit boring and suggested adding dynamic elements such as flying through asteroids or spontaneous ship actions in autopilot mode.</p>					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	5	5	4	5	4	4
Lost in the Kismet						
Task	Task 1			Task 2		
	You find yourself in a room you must escape from. This is only possible if you advance to the next level. Solve the puzzle and proceed to the next room.			You want to escape the room. This is only possible after solving a series of puzzles. Find the answers and complete the game.		
Person 1	The user lit the torch and proceeded to the next level in the game within 45 seconds—without any issues.			The tester became deeply immersed in the game and remained mostly silent throughout. After 7 minutes of gameplay, the user completed the entire game.		
Comments	<p>The user stated that they would extend the game. After learning that it was only a demo and that the full version had to be purchased, they said they would be willing to buy it—if they didn’t wear glasses—since playing caused eye strain. The tester noted that a VR escape room game has much greater potential than a standard app, as it allows full immersion rather than simply tapping on a screen.</p> <p>They said the navigation was very well designed but suggested improving the graphics, which they considered to be low quality. Overall, the tester found it a very interesting experience.</p>					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Engagement
	4	5	3	0	4	4
Person 2	The user managed to light the torch within 30 seconds. The avatar’s “virtual” pants caused some excitement. They proceeded to the next level without any issues.			After 5 minutes of gameplay, the tester gave up on solving the rest of the puzzles due to eye strain and fatigue caused by the game. The user was very close to completing the entire task.		
Comments	<p>The tester, playing Lost in the Kismet—a VR escape room game—was initially very excited about the immersive virtual world around them. However, after a while, it became exhausting. The user suggested improving the graphics, as they resembled “computer games from 10 years ago.” The core concept of transferring a real escape room into virtual reality was seen as a very interesting idea. The main drawback noted was eye strain.</p>					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Engagement
	3	3	3	1	4	4
Person 3	The user lit the torch and advanced to the next level after 1 minute and 30 seconds.			After 9 minutes and 20 seconds, the user completed another level in the game. However,		

	There were noticeable difficulties navigating the app—not due to controls, but rather its level of difficulty.		they experienced frustration due to the lengthy wait time for actions to trigger when staring at objects—it simply "took too long."			
Comments	The game gave the tester a "wow" effect in terms of concept and execution. However, they noted the cursor's delayed reaction time was irritating, as it took too long for interactions to occur when the pointer was directed at something. The graphics were considered adequate—not impressive, but acceptable. The tester pointed out the game's potential to teach logical thinking and stated it was an enjoyable experience that really "pulled them in."					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Engagement
	5	3	4	4	5	5
Person 4	At the beginning, the user was a bit disoriented and scared that something might "jump out" unexpectedly. They didn't notice the countdown timer displayed at the start of the game, which delayed their entry into the gameplay. Controlling the game wasn't a problem; rather, the puzzles posed the main challenge. After 1 minute and 50 seconds, the user successfully progressed to the next level.		The user was immediately excited by the surrounding virtual world and objects, exploring the environment and actively looking around. As they stated, the challenge lay not in navigation, but in solving the puzzles. Their excitement and curiosity lasted for the first 4 minutes and remained fairly high throughout. After 11 minutes, the user completed the entire game without much assistance from the moderator.			
Comments	Throughout the test, the user was highly engaged. One feature they missed was the ability to interact with a "trapped" woman visible through a barred window; they suggested her rescue as an excellent narrative element to enhance the gameplay. The user compared the experience to an animated "Scooby-Doo" episode with similar puzzle-solving elements and praised the concept. They found constantly having to turn their head tiring and would have preferred a zoomed-out view to avoid that. The graphics were described as "good" but in need of improvement. The tester noted that the game could teach logical and abstract thinking to young users and concluded that the experience was enjoyable and fun.					
Ratings	Innovation	User Experience design	User Interface design	Educational Value	Entertainment	Engagement
	5	4	4	4	5	4

Source: (Own elaboration, 2018)

Appendix 2. Usability Test Results (Score Ratings)

Name	Innovation	User Experience	User Interface	Educational Value	Entertainment	Attention Absorption
Anatomy 4D (AR)						
Person 1	4	5	3	3	2	2
Person 2	4	4	4	3	3	3
Person 3	5	5	4	4	4	5
Person 4	5	5	5	5	2	3
<u>Average</u>	<u>4,5</u>	<u>4,75</u>	<u>4,0</u>	<u>3,75</u>	<u>2,75</u>	<u>3,25</u>
Tłumacz Google (AR)						
Person 1	3	5	5	2	1	3
Person 2	4	4	5	4	3	4
Person 3	4	3	4	4	3	4
Person 4	5	5	5	5	2	3
<u>Average</u>	<u>4,0</u>	<u>4,25</u>	<u>4,75</u>	<u>3,75</u>	<u>2,25</u>	<u>3,5</u>

Titans of Space (VR)						
Person 1	4	4	3	4	2	3
Person 2	5	4	3	4	5	5
Person 3	5	3	3	4	5	5
Person 4	5	5	4	5	4	4
<u>Average</u>	<u>4,75</u>	<u>4,0</u>	<u>3,25</u>	<u>4,25</u>	<u>4,0</u>	<u>4,25</u>
Lost In The Kismet (VR)						
Person 1	4	5	3	0	4	4
Person 2	3	3	3	1	4	4
Person 3	5	3	4	4	5	5
Person 4	5	4	4	4	5	4
<u>Average</u>	<u>4,25</u>	<u>3,75</u>	<u>3,5</u>	<u>2,25</u>	<u>4,5</u>	<u>4,25</u>

Source: (Own elaboration, 2018)